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The Impact of Lean Management Practices on Sustainable Performance of Handicraft Enterprises in Vietnam

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Abstract:

Although the taste for handicrafts is increasing, Vietnamese handicraft enterprises still face many difficulties in improving sustainable efficiency. In this context, the implementation of lean management has become one of the best solutions for enterprises. However, Vietnamese handicraft enterprises have usually to consider financial sources to implement lean management because of their small scale and many businesses do not dare to take risks. This study was conducted to empirically examine the effect of LMP on sustainable performance of handicraft enterprises in Vietnam. By analyzing data obtained from 322 handicraft enterprises in Vietnam, the positive effect of lean management practices on sustainable performance was found. lean management not only directly improves sustainable performance, but also helps Vietnamese handicraft enterprises improve their ability to innovate products, innovate processes and implement CSR. This also entails further increasing the benefits of lean management practices. Finally, some policy suggestions have been made to improve the sustainable performance of handicraft enterprises in Vietnam through the implementation of lean management.

Keywords: lean management practices, sustainable performance, handicraft enterprises

1. Introduction

Globalization offers wider opportunities for economies, helping businesses increase production and distribution needs. But this also entails ecological consequences and harms human health. To solve these problems, governments are introducing regulations that make businesses more environmentally friendly. However, some environmentally and socially sustainable projects are costly (e.g., ISO 14000 environmental management system adoption, energy consumption reduction measures). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) projects are also considered capital intensive (Walker et al., 2019). Therefore, the link between lean management practices (LMP) and sustainable development is of increasing interest. Lean management

focuses on reducing waste through resource optimization (Dey et al., 2019), so it is considered an economic-promoting solution while still being environmentally friendly.

In Vietnam, the handicraft industry is always in the TOP 10 of the largest export items, with an export value of about 1.7 billion USD/year (Ministry of Industry and Trade, 2020). There are many product groups that are highly appreciated in the market such as bamboo and rattan products, lacquer products, silk handicraft products, artificial flowers, etc. In addition, handicraft industry also plays an important role in the transformation of rural economic structure. More than 10 million laborers are working in craft villages, thereby contributing to poverty alleviation in rural areas. Up to now, Vietnam has more than 5,441 active craft villages, of which 1,864 craft villages are recognized according to the Government's criteria for craft villages. However, Vietnamese handicrafts firms are experiencing a sharp decline in orders in major markets such as the US and Japan due to challenges in meeting the rules of origin and origin certification procedures, commitments on labor and the environment. Traditional handicraft industries generate various wastes and are not really sustainable (Reni and Anna, 2016). Especially in the current context, craft villages in general and handicraft villages in particular use child labor and idle farm labor. Besides, the environment is also a big problem for Vietnamese handicraft villages. Therefore, this study focuses on sustainable performance in handicraft enterprises in Vietnam.

Previous literature has shown a link between LMP and economic sustainability (Martínez-Jurado and Moyono-Fuentes, 2014). LMP facilitates the adoption of green manufacturing principles and enhances the sustainable performance of many manufacturing companies. However, developments on the impact of LMP on environmental sustainability are still inconclusive because of the appearance of positive (in King and Lenox, 2001) and negative (Rothenberg et al., 2001).

Sustainability-driven innovation can be achieved through product and process innovation (Klewitz and Hansen, 2014). To improve the sustainable performance of products, businesses must consider eco-design. Cleaner production is an example of process innovation for environmental sustainability (Adams et al., 2016). Although previous literature has asserted that both LMP and innovation are supportive factors for achieving sustainability, their impact on the sustainability performance of handicraft businesses in Vietnam is still very limited. In addition, studies in Vietnam have not confirmed the mediating role of CSR in the relationship between LMP and sustainable performance of enterprises, especially there has not been any research examining this issue in handicraft enterprises

To address questions of sustainable performance and to find answers to unconfirmed effects, this paper focuses on the impact between LMP and sustainable performance and determines whether CSR and innovation whether there is an intermediary role in this impact in Vietnamese handicraft enterprises. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Part two presents the theoretical background related to LMP and sustainable performance, and then presents the research hypotheses and models. Part three explains the methods, measures, and the data collection process in the context of Vietnamese handicraft enterprises. Section four describes the results of the study and finally discusses the results, limitations, and future research directions.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Lean management practices and sustainable performance

2.1.1. Lean management practices

LMP has been in the industry for over 40 years as a road map to improve business performance (Emiliani, 2006). The concept of LMP was first mentioned by Womack et al. (1990) in "The Machine That Changed the World" in 1990 and then gradually became a topic of popular interest in the manufacturing field. Lean Manufacturing is defined as the systematic removal of waste from every part of the value stream. "Value

stream” can be defined as the totality of activities aimed at obtaining finished products from raw materials (Womack and Jones, 1996).

Implementing LMP brings a number of benefits such as: cost reduction, increased production efficiency, quality improvement, reduced lead time, reduced supply, flexibility and improved customer satisfaction. (Womack et al., 1990; Womack and Jones, 1996). Lean manufacturing is a combination of total quality management practices, just in time, total preventive maintenance, and human resource management (Shah and Ward, 2003). According to Shah and Ward (2007), the main aim of LMP is to achieve “zero waste” in production, highest quality and resource/energy optimization.

PK Dey et al (2019) measured LMP through three aspects: (1) Waste reduction practices, (2) Productivity enhancement practices and (3) Stakeholder management practices. In there:

- Practice waste reduction: The main goal of Lean Manufacturing is to eliminate waste (Muda in Japanese). Ohno (1988) defines “Muda” as all human activities that do not bring any added value to customers. He identified seven sources of waste including: overproduction, defects, transportation, Waiting, inventory, over/incorrect handling, and displacement. From the perspective of applying LMP in the supply chain, PK Dey et al (2019) have divided waste forms according to three aspects: waste related to suppliers, waste related to customers and waste operating costs of the business.
- Practice improving productivity: lean manufacturing is a strategic tool that helps businesses stay ahead of their competitors by adding value to their products and improving productivity while maintaining a healthy competitive environment (Rohani and Zahraee, 2015). Productivity-enhancing practices include total quality management, overall performance maintenance, statistical process control, inventory management, and capacity optimization.
- Stakeholder management practices: Stakeholders are the objects that interact with the business and make its operations possible (Palang and Dhattrak, 2021). LMP provides methods to help businesses optimize the ability to cooperate and link stakeholders including Supplier relationship management, customer relationship management, employee involvement and management commitment.

2.1.2. Sustainable performance

As sustainability was integrated into the business domain, the concept of corporate sustainability was born and subsequently redefined by academics as “a business and investment strategy that aims to use business best practices to meet and balance the needs of current and future stakeholders” (Artiach et al., 2010). For businesses, sustainability is defined as the right combination of three aspects of economy, environment and society (Elkington, 1994).

Specifically, a business that pursues sustainable growth and survival must consider meeting its business goals, improving its market position, generating sustainable profitable growth, and enhancing its competitive capabilities. Accordingly, the sustainability performance of an enterprise is a measure to quantify and evaluate the sustainability of an enterprise, measuring the extent to which a business incorporates economic, environmental and social factors into its sustainability, and how these factors ultimately affect business and society (Lourenço et al., 2011). There is a great deal of literature on sustainability, however, most have prioritized environment factor that ignores or downplays economic and social aspects (Buyukozkan and Karabulut, 2018). Meanwhile, there are only a few studies on sustainable effects in the handicraft industry.

Businesses are increasingly inclined to achieve sustainability by adopting green initiatives (Teixeira et al., 2012). Economic efficiency is the financial benefit through return on investment and cost reduction throughout the supply chain (Eltayeb et al., 2011), as measured by productivity, profitability, revenue, cost reduction and business growth, etc. (Abdul-Rashid et al., 2017). Business growth is another measure of economic performance. Meanwhile, environmental efficiency is the ecological result of preserving, protecting and taking care of the environment. Environmental performance is highly dependent on energy

use, resource optimization and waste reduction, which has a direct relationship with CO₂ emissions (Yusuf et al., 2013). Finally, social sustainability measures the performance of a business in relation to its impact on other interested parties (communities, employees, suppliers, etc.). This includes topics of business ethics such as: participatory decision making, community commitment, honesty and corruption, or improving the quality of life of all stakeholders (Yusuf et al., 2013). Social performance is measured through investments in CSR projects, employee welfare initiatives, accident reduction, etc. Social performance not only ensures the business can create profits but also ensure that production and business activities do not cause social degradation (Tsai and Chou, 2009).

2.1.3. Relationship between healthy management practices and sustainable performance

The relationship between LMP and performance has been tested by different methods such as theoretical study by Azevedo et al (2012), secondary data analysis study by Hong et al. (2014), etc. Some studies provide evidence that a positive relationship between LMP and sustained performance is not supported (Hajmohammad et al., 2013). Hallam and Contreras (2016) have noted that although LMP and environmental practices share the same goal of reducing waste, both philosophies can also work against each other. Inman and Green (2018) suggested that LMP alone may not help a business achieve its sustainability goals and may never be enough to address all sustainability issues.

However, there is still a lot of opinion and empirical evidence that LMP has a positive impact on sustainability performance (King and Lenox, 2001; Mart´nez-Jurado and Moyono-Fuentes, 2014). Especially in the handicraft sector, where waste is not considered worthless but is gradually becoming a raw material for production activities thanks to green initiatives (Reni and Anna, 2016). Since the raw materials are mainly natural ingredients, the waste in the handicraft industry is an organic waste that can be recovered and reused. Handicraft businesses can achieve economic sustainability through reducing waste in the supply chain (Arkader, 2001), optimizing inventory, helping to optimize supply chain costs, and minimizing risk through investment in R&D and technology, thereby improving the quality of products and services. As a result, LMP has been used to eliminate waste, improve quality, reduce costs, and increase flexibility across supply chains at different levels (Inman and Green, 2018). In addition, the application of LMP helps to achieve environmental and social sustainability through building collaborative relationships among all stakeholders (Inman and Green, 2018). From the above arguments, the study proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: LMP has a positive impact on sustainable performance

2.2. Mediating roles of innovation

2.2.1. Innovation in the handicraft industry

According to Oyekunle and Sirayi (2018), handicraft businesses are susceptible to market upheavals and trends; thus, they must be able to compete in the marketplace. Innovation capability may aid craft enterprises in developing and achieving a competitive advantage in terms of product quality, price, and cost. A redesign of a product might, for instance, result in decreased material use, which not only improves the product's appearance and functioning, but also reduces the product's cost and, thus, its selling price (Oyekunle and Sirayi, 2018). Therefore, innovation capability is vital to the competitive advantage and success of a business (Calantone et al., 2002; Keskin, 2006). Notably, the handicraft industry strives for continuing innovation and capability by fortifying and promoting its traditions, skills, and practicability to fulfill the needs of domestic and international markets (Sanchezmedina et al., 2011). Therefore, inventive ability is necessary for the survival and competitiveness of handicraft firms. Although the significance of innovation in microbusinesses has been well recognized in the literature, innovation and creativeness in handicraft items has remained a contentious subject (Alonso and Bressan 2014). We contend that handicraft microenterprises struggle with competition from machinemade substitutes and the changing preferences of customers (Barber and Krivoshlykova 2006; Yang et al. 2018); therefore, it is necessary for these firms to

adopt innovation in order to survive and compete in the market (Mendozaramrez and Toledolórquez 2014). We argue that these companies are active in product and process innovation, as will be explained below.

Product innovation includes the creation of new goods or substantial enhancements to current ones (Chang et al. 2012). In the case of handicrafts, product innovation includes alterations in form, shape, and the addition of value and distinctive patterns (Chand et al. 2014; Mendozaramrez and Toledolópez 2014). Relevant literature indicates that product innovation includes improvements or changes in shape, size, texture, and design, as well as additions to the product's value and design distinctiveness (Chand et al. 2014; Girón et al. 2007; Mendozaramrez and Toledolópez 2014; Sánchezmedina et al. 2011; Zhan and Walker, 2018).

Process innovation entails significant modifications to procedures and equipment (OECD, 2005), as well as enhancements to production techniques (Polder et al. 2010). The objective is not just to develop new and unique goods, but also to adapt current ones. Process innovation include the introduction of never-before-used tools, equipment, and technology, as well as modifications to the processes of manufacturing or development of artisanal products (Polder et al. 2010). In addition, process innovation includes the modification of production techniques, the use of new or different materials, quality raw materials, technology, machinery, tools, and the replacement of equipment (Chand et al. 2014; Craft Council Report 2012; Ghosh 2012; Mendozaramrez and Toledolóz 2014; Sánchezmedina et al., 2011).

2.2.2. Lean management practices and innovation

Following the release of "The Machine That Changed the World" by Womack et al. (1990), the phrase "lean management" garnered tremendous attention and popularity. According to the authors, the objective of lean management is perfection, which is shown by enhanced efficiency, a reduction in defects and inventory, and an expansion of product diversity. Shah and Ward (2003) characterized lean management as "a multidimensional strategy that integrates a broad range of management approaches, such as just-in-time, quality systems, work teams, cellular manufacturing, and supplier management." Liker and Franz (2011) described lean management as "the continual elimination of waste via problem-solving in pursuit of excellence." Based on the above rationale, lean management is described as a systematic technique to detect and remove waste via continuous improvement; the flow of the product in search of perfection in response to consumer demand (Bhasin, 2015). Also noted is that Lean is not about adopting a set of tools. Instead, we are advised that it must center on fostering a lean or continuous-improvement culture, developing people-focused leaders, and increasing lean literacy (Schonberger, 2019).

Several academics have used lean ideas to develop so-called lean innovation models. Srinivasan (2010) proposes that lean and innovation may be complimentary and translates lean concepts into goals for innovation management. Other approaches emphasize stakeholder value orientation for incremental innovation and seek to maximize radical innovation output with constrained resources (Bicen & Johnson, 2015). Sehested and Sonnenberg (2011) relativize criticism of the application of lean principles to innovation by identifying lean innovation as a distinct management concept, as opposed to scientifically analyzing interdependencies in a rigorous way. Based on this reasoning, the following hypotheses may be formulated:

H2a: LMP has a positive impact on product innovation

H2b: LMP has a positive impact on process innovation

2.2.3. Innovation and sustainable performance

Innovation capability is vital to a business's success. Keskin (2006) and Calantone et al. (2002), for example, found that innovation capability significantly increases a company's performance. In addition, Weber and Heidenreich (2018) found that cooperation across vertical and horizontal partners significantly increases innovation capacity and company performance. Therefore, innovation capability is a crucial internal resource for performance enhancement.

Additionally, innovation capability improves performance by reducing expenditures and increasing the profit margin. Moreover, according to Yang et al. (2018), the majority of handcraft businesses in developing countries struggle to compete with machine-made products, and employment in this sector is declining. Therefore, by increasing their ability for innovation, small businesses can not only compete with mass-produced items, but also preserve cultural traditions, retain and attract the next generation. By matching product characteristics to market need, microentrepreneurs in the handicraft industry may achieve personal happiness, fulfillment, and increased customer satisfaction. In addition, the increased level of innovative skills may help these enterprises express and realize their creative vision, as well as promote and preserve their cultural identity for transmission to future generations. Therefore, innovative aptitude contributes to the economic, non-economic, and cultural success of enterprises. Thus, microbusinesses in the field of handicrafts may achieve sustained growth. Based on this reasoning, the following hypotheses may be formulated:

H3a: Product innovation has a positive impact on sustainable performance

H3b: Process innovation has a positive impact on sustainable performance

2.3. Mediating roles of CSR Practices

2.3.1. CSR Practices in the handicraft industry

CSR is the strategic integration of environmental and social practices inside a firm (Martinez-Conesa, Soto-Acosta and Carayannis, 2017). Environmental and social practices throughout the supply chain are also referred to as green supply chain management practices. These practices include green product development, green design, green procurement, green manufacturing/operations, green logistics, and green marketing (Luthra et al., 2011) as well as key elements for achieving sustainability performance. These methods, practices, and strategies may result in cheaper costs, higher production, and an improved image with customers and the community for the green manufacturer. Sambrani and Pol (2016) and Sarkis et al. (2011) provide exhaustive literature on corporate social responsibility.

During the 1950s and 1960s, the notion of corporate social responsibility emerged. According to the World Bank, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is widely described as an organization's commitment to contribute to sustainable economic development by engaging with workers, their families, the local community, and society at large to improve their quality of life. CSR has shown to be an effective technique for boosting the Handicraft industry. Corporations are seeing that the Handicraft industry has fallen behind. Therefore, some corporations are actively promoting handicrafts by giving craftspeople with technical, financial, and marketing aid. It encompasses all efforts made to maintain and preserve the national history, arts, and culture.

2.3.2. Lean management practices and CSR Practices

As green supply chain efforts, CSR (i.e., environmental, and social practices) across the supply chain has been characterized. Prior study demonstrates that there are synergies between the 'lean' and 'green' methodologies, since they both stress research and energy efficiency, waste and emission reduction in conjunction with increased production (Inman and Green, 2018). In addition, whereas 'lean' and 'green' independently contribute to the sustainability of SME supply chains, LMP influences economic, environmental, and social performance to achieve total sustainability performance through the mediation impact of environmental and social practices.

When a firm implements lean management, it may simultaneously enhance production efficiency, working conditions, and environmental impact, all of which help to CSR implementation. Companies may thus use lean manufacturing to incorporate CSR. Lean manufacturing strategies provide CSR advantages, especially in the areas of environmental preservation and working condition enhancement (King & Lenox, 2001). Lean management contributes to the reduction of material waste and the recycling of materials. Therefore, the organization engages in trash removal at the source as opposed to using end-of-pipe treatment procedures. In addition, lean management may reduce pollution by lowering the marginal cost of pollution control

operations and motivating managers to invest in waste reduction. It can be said that lean management will enable companies to better implement CSR, particularly environmental CSR and working conditions, towards a sustainable business model, because CSR is integrated into the company's daily operations as an integral part, rather than as an add-on, such as charitable activities or marketing campaigns to promote the company's brand image. Based on this reasoning, the following hypotheses may be formulated:

H4a: LMP has a positive effect on environmental CSR practices

H4b: LMP has a positive effect on social CSR practices

2.3.3. CSR Practices and sustainable performance

Corporate sustainability is described as the optimal mix of economic, environmental, and social factors (Elkington, 1994). To achieve sustainability, an increasing number of companies are implementing green initiatives (Teixeira, Jabbour and de Sousa, 2012). Sustainability is achieved by organizations via economic and operational consequences. Economic outcomes include financial gains via investment return and supply chain cost reduction (Eltayeb, Zailani and Ramayah, 2011). The expansion of businesses is another indicator of economic results. The link between operational results (i.e., productivity) and sustainability performance, which leads to economic success, is direct. CO₂ emissions are directly related to energy consumption, resource optimization, and waste reduction, which are crucial to environmental performance (Yusuf et al., 2013). Social performance refers to the improvement of the quality of life for all interested parties (Yusuf et al., 2013). This is quantified by expenditures in CSR projects, staff wellness programs, accident reduction, etc. Social sustainability assures not just that industry is profitable, but also that industrial operations do not result in social deterioration (Tsai and Chou, 2009).

The connection between sustainable performance and CSR strategy has attracted a growing number of researchers recently. Bevan and Yung (2015) analyzed the adoption of these practices among SMEs and discovered some socially responsible actions, despite the lack of a structured plan to do so; nonetheless, the emphasis is on economic performance issues. Golini et al. (2014) investigated manufacturers' environmental and social strategies. They discovered that performance has improved after using such rules. Schaltegger and Burritt (2010) concluded that socially responsible programs reduce risk and costs. Lopez et al. (2007) explored whether firms' sustainable performance is influenced by a socially responsible strategy; they found that the discrepancies in their performance are due to divergent social visions. Interestingly, the study revealed a negative correlation between sustainable performance and socially responsible behavior. In addition, Jain et al. (2017) have observed no significant effect of ecological and social activities on performance.

Despite past efforts to investigate the influence of company strategies on sustainable performance, there is a need for more explanation, especially in settings of emerging countries (Alikaj et al., 2017). Based on this reasoning, the following hypotheses may be formulated:

H5a: Environmental CSR practices has a positive effect on sustainable performance

H5b: Social CSR practices has a positive effect on sustainable performance

3. Methodology

3.1. Measure

Measurements of LMP are adopted from Shah and Ward (2003, 2007); Inman and Green (2018). LMP is divided into 3 dimensions: All forms of resource waste management (3-items), Productivity enhancement programs (5-items), and Stakeholders' management (4-items).

Measurements of innovation are adopted from Mendozaramírez and Toledolópez (2014); Yang and Shafi (2019). Product Innovation is divided into 3 dimensions: Value adding (3-items), Product improvement (3-items) and Design uniqueness (3-items). Process Innovation is divided into 3 dimensions:

Changes or replacement of tools, equipment, and machinery (3-items), Alternative/ New Materials (3-items) and Quality material (3-items).

Measurements of CSR practices are adopted from Baumgartner (2013); Martinez-Conesa et al. (2017);. Both two dimension of CSR practices (Environmental and Social) are each measured by 3-items.

Measurements of sustainability performance are adopted from Inman and Green (2018); Abdul-Rashid et al. (2017); Adebajo et al. (2016). Sustainability performance is divided into 3 dimensions: Economic performance (4-items), Environmental performance (3-items), and social performance (3-items).

3.2. Sample and data analysis

In Vietnam, the handicraft industry is always in the TOP 10 of the largest export items, with an export value of about 1.7 billion USD/year. Up to now, Vietnamese handicraft products have been present in 163 countries and territories, accounting for nearly 10% of the global market's demand. Vietnam's handicraft export turnover in the period 2015-2019 increased by an average of 9.5% per year, from 1.62 billion USD (2015) to 2.23 billion USD (2019), expected to reach nearly 4 billion USD by 2025. According to statistics of the Vietnam Handicraft Export Association (VIETCRAFT, 2020), for every 1 million USD of handicraft exports, profits are 5 - 10 times that of the mining industry, the export content is very high. However, at present, Vietnamese handicrafts are experiencing a sharp decline in orders in major markets such as the US and Japan due to challenges in meeting the rules of origin certification procedures, commitments on labor and the environment. Traditional handicraft industries generate various wastes and are not really sustainable (Reni and Anna, 2016) . Especially in the current context, craft villages in general and handicraft villages in particular use child labor and idle farm labor. Global and Vietnamese consumers are increasingly concerned about environmental and social issues, especially issues related to the origin and legality of raw materials used, issues related to labor practices, worker safety and health, clean production - environmentally friendly, etc.

With the goal of increasing sales, many handicraft businesses try to make good use of the main materials they use. For example, pottery businesses have taken advantage of excess clay during the cutting process to reuse as much as possible. In addition, gas furnaces are used instead of wood and coal furnaces to reduce fuel consumption, production costs and save time. And based on the design features of these ovens, it is possible to process more products at once. In addition, many artisans have designed their own equipment and machines, innovated production processes, and replaced safe materials to seek clean certification for handicrafts. Handicraft products using recycled and salvaged materials and fair-trade channels are forecasted to be increasingly developed. Environmental issues show that the study of sustainability is essential for handicraft enterprises in Vietnam to have the advantage of market expansion and long-term development. Some handicraft enterprises are increasingly interested in the optimal use of materials, innovating processes, and caring for the environment in order to avoid waste, improve productivity and achieve clean certification. This context is antecedent, making it possible for the objective of the study: to explore the impact of LMPs on sustainable performance and to identify the mediating role of innovation and CSR practices in this relationship in handicraft enterprises in Vietnam.

In summary, this study takes the context of handicraft enterprises in Vietnam to study the influence of LMP on the sustainable performance of these enterprises. First, randomly selected businesses will receive a Gmail notification of research information. If there is no response from the business after 2 weeks, the invitation to respond will be sent again. Businesses that agree will be scheduled to be interviewed in person or through an online questionnaire. Through conducting a survey of senior leaders of Vietnamese handicraft enterprises, this study obtained 322 valid observations for use in quantitative data analysis. These are all businesses that have been operating for at least 3 years in the handicraft industry and have full business results reports that are considered important and reliable data sources.

3.3. Data analysis

The hypotheses in the research model have been tested through SEM and in particular the PLS-SEM method (Hair et al., 2019). Measurement, structure and model estimation tests are performed on SmartPLS software (Ringle et al., 2015). At present, theoretical models on the influence of lean management practices on sustainable performance in Vietnam have not been agreed, so the PLS-SEM method is more appropriate (Hair et al., 2014). Another reason for choosing PLS-SEM is because the sample size is not too large with only 332 observations, and the survey data does not guarantee a normal distribution. PLS-SEM is a collection of statistical techniques, which can be divided into two phases with the corresponding criteria:

Table 1. Criteria for evaluating model

			References
Measurement model	Convergent validity of items	Outer loading > 0.7	Henseler et al. (2009)
	Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha > 0.7	Hair et al. (2014)
		Composite reliability > 0.7	Hair et al. (2014)
	Discriminant validity	HTMT < 0.85	Henseler et al. (2015)
	Convergent validity of variables	AVE > 0.5	Hair et al. (2014)
Multicollinearity	Outer VIF < 5	Hair et al. (2014)	
Structural model	R-square	Weak: $R^2 < 0.33$ Moderate: $0.33 < R^2 < 0.67$ Strong: $R^2 > 0.67$	Chin (1998)
		SRMR < 0.08	Hu and Bentler (1999)
	Model-fit	RMS Theta < 0.12	Henseler et al. (2014)

4. Data analysis and results

To ensure the convergent validity of the items, Outer loading was used as a criterion to remove non-conforming items (Henseler et al., 2009). The results show that the items LMP2, LMP4, LMP12, PDI9, PCI1, SP2 are all removed due to Outer loading < 0.7 (Henseler et al., 2009). After removing these items, the criteria for convergence of the remaining items are satisfied (Henseler et al., 2009). Based on the obtained model, the results of evaluating the measurement model for reliability and convergence (Table 2) show that the criteria are satisfied (Hair et al., 2014).

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and AVE

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
ENV	0.854	0.911	0.774
LMP	0.910	0.926	0.581
PCI	0.901	0.921	0.592
PDI	0.935	0.946	0.687
SOC	0.792	0.878	0.705
SP	0.926	0.939	0.630

About the discriminant validity of the variables, the results (table 3) show that there is no value of HTMT exceeding 0.85, satisfying the suggestion of Henseler et al. (2015).

Table 3: HTMT

	ENV	LMP	PCI	PDI	SOC	SP
ENV						
LMP	0.418					
PCI	0.124	0.461				
PDI	0.119	0.256	0.211			
SOC	0.087	0.293	0.195	0.190		
SP	0.235	0.500	0.472	0.318	0.327	

The results in Table 4 also show that the problem of multicollinearity is still accepted because the largest VIF coefficient of 3.761 is still less than 5, as suggested by Hair et al (2019).

Table 4: VIF

Items	VIF	Items	VIF	Items	VIF	Items	VIF	Items	VIF
ENV1	2.574	LMP6	1.974	PCI6	1.945	PDI5	2.438	SP10	2.488
ENV2	2.413	LMP7	2.291	PCI7	1.963	PDI6	3.761	SP3	2.279
ENV3	1.778	LMP8	2.344	PCI8	1.828	PDI7	3.423	SP4	2.667
LMP1	1.875	LMP9	2.493	PCI9	2.000	PDI8	3.223	SP5	2.449
LMP10	2.021	PCI2	2.676	PDI1	2.989	SOC1	1.899	SP6	2.255
LMP11	2.361	PCI3	1.963	PDI2	2.323	SOC2	1.463	SP7	1.881
LMP3	1.805	PCI4	1.774	PDI3	2.720	SOC3	1.888	SP8	2.769
LMP5	1.921	PCI5	2.130	PDI4	2.857	SP1	1.793	SP9	2.297

After removing nonconforming items, the measurement quality evaluation criteria are satisfied. Based on the results in Table 5, the model-fit evaluation indexes of SRMR and rms Theta are satisfied (Hair et al., 2019). In addition, the coefficient $R^2 = 0.337$ showed that the research model explained 33.7% of the variation in sustainable performance. This result, although not very impressive, is still acceptable.

Table 5: SRMR, rms Theta, R2

	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.051
rms Theta	0.098
R2 (SP)	0.337

The results in Table 6 show that the relationship between LMP and ENV, LMP and PCI have a strong correlation. Thereby, it shows that the change of LMP can greatly affect the practice of environmental CSR and process innovation of handicraft enterprises in Vietnam. In addition, with the coefficient $f\text{-square} = 0.005 < 0.02$, the implementation of environmental CSR does not seem to have an impact on the sustainable performance of handicraft enterprises in Vietnam.

Table 6: f-square

	ENV	PCI	PDI	SOC	SP
ENV					0.005
LMP	0.159	0.213	0.061	0.069	0.064
PCI					0.086
PDI					0.034
SOC					0.031

Through the bootstrap test, the estimation results of the structural equation model are shown in Figure 2 and table 7. The results show that the impact of environmental CSR management practices on the sustainable performance of handicraft enterprises is not statistically significant. This result rejected hypothesis H5b. On the other hand, the remaining effects are all positive and statistically significant, so the remaining hypotheses are accepted.

Figure 2: Model estimation results

After testing the statistical hypotheses, LMP still has a positive impact on sustainable performance. This suggests that improving LMP will directly improve the sustainable performance of handicraft enterprises. In addition, when enterprises implement LMP well, it also helps to improve process innovation capacity ($\beta = 0.419$). Not only that, the better application of LMP also helps enterprises to improve both product innovation capacity ($\beta = 0.240$) and ability to practice CSR in both environmental aspects ($\beta = 0.370$) and ($\beta = 0.254$). In short, LMP not only helps handicraft enterprises to improve sustainable efficiency but also increases other advantages such as innovation and CSR implementation.

For the factors promoting sustainable performance, process innovation plays the most important role ($\beta = 0.266$). This is appropriate because the benefits of process innovation will help businesses overcome many difficulties in the production process of handicrafts. Besides, product innovation also has a significant influence on sustainable performance ($\beta = 0.157$) and shows that more attention to product and product innovation is necessary for handicraft enterprises. technology in Vietnam. In addition, the implementation of CSR policies towards society also helps to improve sustainable performance relatively ($\beta = 149$).

Table 7: Model estimation results

Hypothesis	Effect	Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values	Support
H5a	ENV -> SP	0.065	1.264	0.206	Rejected
H4a	LMP -> ENV	0.370	7.064	0.000	Supported
H2b	LMP -> PCI	0.419	8.747	0.000	Supported
H2a	LMP -> PDI	0.240	4.953	0.000	Supported
H4b	LMP -> SOC	0.254	4.601	0.000	Supported
H1	LMP -> SP	0.252	5.058	0.000	Supported
H3a	PCI -> SP	0.266	5.759	0.000	Supported
H3b	PDI -> SP	0.157	3.420	0.001	Supported
H5b	SOC -> SP	0.149	2.933	0.003	Supported

Through detailed impact testing, LMP not only affects SPM directly but also indirectly through PDI, PCI, and CSR implementation to society. This result further confirms the benefits of implementing lean management for Vietnamese handicraft enterprises.

Table 8: Mediating roles

	Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values
LMP -> PDI -> SP	0.038	2.716	0.007
LMP -> ENV -> SP	0.024	1.213	0.225
LMP -> PCI -> SP	0.112	4.680	0.000
LMP -> SOC -> SP	0.038	2.298	0.022

5. Conclusion

Research results have confirmed the positive influence of LMP on products of handicraft enterprises in Vietnam. This result supports previous studies such as Vinodh et al. (2011); Viesi et al. (2017); Moreira et al. (2010). For handicraft businesses, cooperation with stakeholders such as customers and suppliers are necessary to maintain and increase competitive advantages in the market. The handicraft industry is a special one because of its limitations in terms of diversity, access to knowledge and resources. Therefore, the lean management helps them to well implement the programs to reduce costs and increase productivity due to optimized resources. This will lay the foundation for the sustainable development of the business. By building relationships with customers, suppliers, employees or making commitments, businesses will have a sustainable foundation to be able to successfully exploit handicraft products on the market. In general, handicraft enterprises in Vietnam need more confidence in implementing lean management. Businesses can organize meetings with customers, suppliers, or employees to understand and agree on issues related to production and management.

The research results also show that LMP not only affects SP directly, but also mediates through process innovation, product innovation, and social CSR management practices. In particular, the role of process innovation and product innovation is most important. This further confirms the role of LMP development for handicraft enterprises in Vietnam. In general, lean management helps to accumulate the necessary resources to innovate processes and create new handicrafts. Through lean management, production costs will be optimized, enterprises will accumulate enough resources to replace, improve tools, equipment, machines or improve the quality of materials. From there, businesses can increase productivity while also improving product quality and achieving sustainable efficiency. Through the implementation of lean management, enterprises also easily optimize the product creation process, thereby facilitating product innovation to maintain good and long-term relationships with customers.

With the continuous innovation of handicraft products, enterprises also approach and keep up with the tastes of more customers, thereby supporting the sustainable development of the business. In addition, with the implementation of better lean management, handicraft enterprises can always face competition from machine-made products (Yang et al. 2018). This is achieved through appropriate product innovation and process innovation without reducing the cultural value of crafts, thereby improving not only economic but also social and environmental performance. In addition, lean management can limit the disappearance of handicrafts by applying modern methods and techniques while still ensuring traditional beauty.

The implementation of the lean governance model also helps businesses have a better awareness of CSR, thereby improving the ability of enterprises to CSR practices. Handicraft enterprises always face many environmental and social problems. Especially when many handicraft industries no longer provide sustainable income, artisans will not be interested and leave this industry. Handicraft businesses that rely on a lean governance model will be able to overcome this through improving their ability to perform social responsibility towards their communities and employees. As a result, they gain more support from stakeholders, making it easier to achieve sustainability goals. In summary, the research results imply that the implementation of lean management towards responsibility and innovation will lead to strong benefits for all parties, especially the sustainable improvement of Vietnamese handicraft enterprises.

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Appendix – measure

Lean Management Practices (Shah and Ward 2003, 2007; Inman and Green, 2018)

Please indicate the extent of implementation of the following practices in your firm. (From 1 = no implementation; to 5 = benchmark implementation)

All forms of resource waste management

1. We have implemented resource waste management program with suppliers
2. We have implemented resource waste management program with customers
3. We have implemented resource waste management program in our operations

Productivity enhancement programs

4. We have implemented TQM effectively
5. We have implemented TPM effectively
6. We have adopted statistical process control in our production
7. We have inventory reduction program in place
8. We have achieved capacity utilization

Stakeholders' management

9. We use effective supplier relationship management practices
10. We use effective customer relationship management practices
11. Our employees are totally involved and committed to firm
12. Our firm's management is totally committed to firm

Innovation (Mendezaramírez and Toledolópez, 2014; Yang and Shafi, 2019)

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following innovation items implemented in your firm during the last three years? (From 1-Strongly disagree to 5-Strongly Agree)

Product Innovation

Value adding

1. Improved and added new features to current products in order to enhance their ease of use and improve customer satisfaction
2. Developed products with technical specifications and functionalities that are different from the existing ones
3. Improved the quality of products to enhance durability and reliability of products

Product improvement

4. Significantly improved size/shape/texture of the products
5. Significantly improved finishing/color of the products
6. Significantly improved quality of the products

Design uniqueness

7. Developed new and unique designs which are different from our competitors
8. Developed unique cultural aspects in designs of the products
9. In comparison to competitors, our firm produced more unique products

Process Innovation

Changes or replacement of tools, equipment, and machinery

1. Modified Technology/Machinery/ tool/ equipment
2. Used new technology in the production process
3. Increased the quality of manufacturing processes, techniques, machinery etc.

Alternative/ New Materials

4. Developed new products that include new materials that are different from what is currently being used
5. Alternative/ New input materials introduced in the production process
6. In comparison to competitors, the raw materials used in products are new

Quality material

7. Improved the quality of materials
8. Increased the quality of the components and materials used in manufacturing of current products
9. In comparison to competitors, our firm uses high quality materials

Corporate social responsibility practices (Baumgartner, 2013; Martinez-Conesa et al., 2017)

Please indicate the extent of implementation of the following practices in your firm (from 1 = no implementation; to 5 = benchmark implementation)

Environmental management practices

1. We practice energy management program
2. We practice waste management program
3. We practice resource optimization program

Social management practices

1. We have implemented employee wellbeing program
2. We have concern for every stakeholder (e.g., customers, suppliers, community etc.)
3. We have undertaken several improvement projects for communities

Sustainability performance (Inman and Green, 2018; Abdul-Rashid et al. 2017; Adebajo et al., 2016)

Please indicate the extent to which you perceive that your firm has achieved each of the following during the past year (from 1 = not at all to 5 = significant)

Economic performance

1. Our productivity has improved
2. Our turnover has increased
3. Our cost has reduced
4. Our business experiences growth

Environmental performance

5. We have reduced energy consumption
6. We have reduced waste across the supply chain
7. We have achieved resource efficiency across the supply chain

Social performance

8. Our employee turnover has reduced
9. We have reduced accident
10. We have enhanced our investment in community-based projects